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Remarking An Analisation

Evaluating the Impact of Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (Pmjay) with Special Reference to Healthcare of Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract

The Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (PMJAY), also known as Ayushman Bharat, is a flagship health insurance scheme launched by the Government of India in 2018 to provide financial protection for healthcare to economically disadvantaged society. This study will critically analyse the implementation and impact of Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (PMJAY), focusing on its role in strengthening primary healthcare in Uttar Pradesh. Uttar Pradesh (UP) is India's most populous and diverse state and faces significant healthcare challenges due to its high population density, rural prevalence, and infrastructure gaps. The study examines the objectives of the scheme, its integration with existing healthcare infrastructure, and its performance in terms of accessibility, affordability, and quality of primary healthcare services. Over **20 million families** are eligible for the scheme in UP, providing potential financial protection for a significant portion of the population. By integrating **primary-level care through** Health and Wellness Centres (**HWCs**). However, its performance in the primary healthcare sector of UP requires a nuanced analysis. This research utilizes quantitative data from governmental reports, surveys, newspapers, magazines etc. The findings highlight significant achievements of PMJAY in increasing healthcare access among vulnerable populations in Uttar Pradesh. This paper concludes with recommendations to enhance the effectiveness of PMJAY, particularly in addressing gaps in primary healthcare delivery. By focusing on localized challenges and leveraging community-based solutions, the scheme can contribute more meaningfully to achieving universal health coverage in Uttar Pradesh and beyond.

Keywords PMJAY, Healthcare, Uttar Pradesh, Health Insurance, Public Health Policy, Ayushman Bharat, Universal Health Coverage.

Introduction

Healthcare in India is characterised by both public and private healthcare, with a heavy reliance on the private sector, particularly in secondary and tertiary healthcare. Despite significant progress in healthcare, access to quality healthcare, particularly at the primary level, remains a challenge. Public health systems, such as central centres, wellness health centres (WHCs) and community health centres (CHCs), are often underfunded, understaffed and under-capacitated, particularly in rural and under-served areas. Non-communicable diseases (NCDs), maternal and child health issues, and infectious diseases place a heavy burden on the system. Moreover, out-of-pocket expenses on healthcare continue to be among the highest in the world, pushing millions of people into poverty each year. While initiatives like the National Health Mission (NHM) focus on promoting primary healthcare, challenges such as fragmented service delivery, inadequate infrastructure, and disparities in access between urban and rural areas continue to hinder progress toward universal health coverage (UHC). These gaps underscore the critical need for schemes like PMJAY to prioritize and strengthen primary care as the foundation of a resilient healthcare system.

The Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (PMJAY), launched in September 2018 under the Ayushman Bharat program, is the flagship health insurance scheme of the Government of India aimed at achieving Universal Health Coverage (UHC). PMJAY provides up to ₹5 lakh

per family per year for secondary and tertiary healthcare to over 10 crore vulnerable families, targeting around 50 crore individuals, approximately 40% of India's population. As of September 2019, it was reported that 18,059 hospitals have been admitted and over 10 crore e-cards have been issued. The scheme focuses on reducing wasteful healthcare expenditures, improving access to quality healthcare services, and enhancing equity by addressing the needs of economically disadvantaged populations. PMJAY works through a partnership of public and private hospitals, using public-private partnerships to provide wider coverage. Apart from medical care, the scheme also aims to integrate Health and Wellness Centres (HWCs) under Ayushman Bharat to strengthen the primary healthcare system and promote preventive care measures.

Studying the role of PMJAY in primary healthcare is important because it provides insights into how the programme can help address chronic inequalities in response to treatment in India. While PMJAY primarily focuses on providing financial protection for secondary and tertiary healthcare services, its integration with Health and Wellness Centres (HWCs) under the Ayushman Bharat programme provides an opportunity to strengthen primary healthcare, which is the foundation of the healthcare institution. Primary healthcare plays a key role in preventive care, early diagnosis, and the management of non-communicable and infectious diseases that contribute to most of the diseases in India. Evaluating the impact of PMJAY on primary care can highlight its potential to promote health equity, reduce the need for hospitalisations, and reduce healthcare costs in the long term. Moreover, understanding its role can support policies to improve access, infrastructure, and service delivery at the primary level, ensuring that the scheme not only treats illnesses but also fosters a healthier population.

Objective of study

The objectives for the present study on the topic "Evaluating the Impact of Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojna (PMJAY): With special reference to Healthcare of Uttar Pradesh" are as follows:

To evaluate the implementation of PMJAY in Uttar Pradesh, with a focus on healthcare.

To analyse the role of PMJAY in strengthening the healthcare network in Uttar Pradesh.

To provide recommendations for improving the scheme's effectiveness

Review of Literature

Omkarnath Sivarchaka and Himadri Mamgain (2024) analysed the Transforming Lives Through Ayushman Bharat Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (AB PMJAY) and concluded that to move forward, PMJAY can play a transformative role in the healthcare landscape, integrate with primary healthcare, contribute to economic development, and expand its scope to include more healthcare services.

Angela Chaudhuri et al. (2023) The study involved developing a theoretical PHC framework, creating search strategies across databases (like MEDLINE, OVID, and CINAHL), and screening them. The review encompassed health innovations and included studies from 1990 to 2019. Relevant quantitative and geographically focused study designs were included, focusing on innovations that improve the efficiency, effectiveness, quality, sustainability, and economy of primary care services. A total of 239 impact evaluations were included and analysed. The studies predominantly took place in rural communities (53%), followed by mixed urban-rural, urban, and tribal communities. Foundations were primary funders (35.6%), with community health worker-delivered interventions, digital service innovations, and supportive mentoring programs being the key supported interventions.

Mayur Trivedi et al. (2022) analysed the Experiences and challenges in accessing hospitalization in a government-funded health insurance scheme: Evidence from early implementation of Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (PM-JAY) in India. The objective of this study is to understand beneficiaries' experience of availing healthcare services at the empanelled hospitals in PM-JAY. This study examines the responsiveness of PM-JAY by measuring the prompt attention in service delivery and access to information by the beneficiaries; the financial burden experienced by the beneficiaries; and beneficiary's satisfaction with the experience of hospitalization under PMJAY and its determinants.

Vinoth Gnana Chellaiyan et al. (2020) analysed the Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana – Ayushman Bharat. The objective of this review is to explore the PMJAY program and to assess how far it could achieve the goal of universal health coverage. The study concluded that It is a major step by the Government of India to fulfil the goal of universal health coverage hence if implemented properly, it could be a game changer.

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Chandrakant Lahariya, (2020) analysed the key design aspects of HWCs, against core components of PHC & the health system functions and also reviewed the progress and analyses of the potential of HWCs to strengthen PHC services and therefore, advance Universal Health Coverage in India. It has been argued that the effectiveness and success of HWCs will be dependent upon a rapid transition from policy to accelerated implementation stage; focus on both supply and demand side interventions, dedicated and increased funding by both union and state governments; appropriate use of information and communication technology; engagement of community and civil society and other stakeholders, focus on effective and functional referral linkages; attention on public health services & population health interventions; sustained political will & monitoring and evaluation for the mid-term corrections, amongst other.

Research Gap

Though there have been many studies on the Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojna (PMJAY) but not much attention has been paid to the Uttar Pradesh healthcare system. The performance of Uttar Pradesh healthcare has not been examined or evaluated so far.

Methodology

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A Research Methodology describes the methods and strategies for gathering and analysing information and data related to a specific research topic.

Research Design

This study employs quantitative research techniques to critically analyse the implementation and impact of the Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (PMJAY) on healthcare in Uttar Pradesh. The research is descriptive and analytical, aimed at evaluating the scheme's effectiveness and identifying challenges specific to the state's healthcare context.

Data Collection

This paper is based on secondary data. The secondary data will be collected from books, journals, and newspapers like The Economic Times and Financial Times. The data will also be collected from government reports, official websites, and academic publications, Ayushman Bharat Digital Mission (ABDM), the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, the National Health Authority, and the Uttar Pradesh Health Department.

Result and Discussion

Key Features of PMJAY

PM-JAY is the world's largest health insurance/ assurance scheme fully financed by the government. It provides a cover of Rs. 5 lakhs per family per year for secondary and tertiary care hospitalization across public and private empanelled hospitals in India. Over 12 crore poor and vulnerable entitled families (approximately 55 crore beneficiaries) are eligible for these benefits. PM-JAY provides cashless access to health care services for the beneficiary at the point of service, that is, the hospital. PM-JAY envisions to help mitigate catastrophic expenditure on medical treatment which pushes nearly 6 crore Indians into poverty each year. It covers up to 3 days of pre-hospitalization and 15 days of post-hospitalization expenses such as diagnostics and medicines. There is no restriction on the family size, age or gender. Benefits of the scheme are portable across the country, beneficiary can visit any empanelled public or private hospital in India to avail cashless treatment. Services include approximately 1,929 procedures covering all the costs related to treatment, including but not limited to drugs, supplies, diagnostic services, physician's fees, room charges, surgeon charges, OT and ICU charges etc. Public hospitals are reimbursed for the healthcare services at par with the private hospitals.

Benefit Cover Under PM-JAY

Benefit cover under various Government-funded health insurance schemes in India has always been structured on an upper ceiling limit ranging from an annual cover of rupees 30,000 to rupees 3,00,000 per family across various States which created a fragmented system. PM-JAY provides cashless cover of up to INR5,00,000 to each eligible family per annum for listed secondary and tertiary care conditions. The scheme includes expenses incurred on the following components of the treatments that are Medical examination, treatment and consultation, Pre-hospitalization Medicine and medical consumables, Non-intensive and intensive care services, Diagnostic and laboratory investigations, Medical

implantation services, Accommodation benefits, Food services, Complications arising during treatment, Post-hospitalization follow-up care up to 15 days.

Hospital Empanelment

The supply of health care services under PM-JAY must be ensured through pre-selected, well-equipped and well-prepared hospitals to deliver the benefits. Also, the hospitals must be distributed widely enough over the geography to ensure optimal accessibility to eligible families.

To cater to the increased demands under PM-JAY and also to ensure quality care to the beneficiaries, it is imperative to maintain and grow a network of hospitals that also conform to the quality standards and criteria. This leads to the need for the empanelment of hospitals on a pre-emptive basis so that beneficiaries are certain of their rights being honoured in the most convenient, cashless and quality manner.

Table 1: District-wise Ayushman Card Creation, Hospital Admission and Hospital Empanelment in Uttar Pradesh

S.No.	District Name	Ayushman card Creation	Hospital Admission	Hospital Empanelment
1	Agra	839263	31410	129
2	Aligarh	1007773	100388	90
3	Ambedkar Nagar	819973	21101	37
4	Amethi	574403	22273	59
5	Amroha	441420	24454	51
6	Auraiya	373445	17568	34
7	Ayodhya	756376	30109	71
8	Azamgarh	1141891	46746	82
9	Baghpat	363049	19465	34
10	Bahraich	948967	52638	87
11	Ballia	909545	38165	62
12	Balrampur	561831	18478	50
13	Banda	499174	14749	26
14	Bara Banki	971764	39992	70
15	Bareilly	1116280	142295	249
16	Basti	749519	36534	102
17	Bhadohi	423915	29976	51
18	Bijnor	1063351	100536	111
19	Budaun	694635	34407	45
20	Bulandshahr	857764	88098	159
21	Chandauli	533167	39181	62
22	Chitrakoot	303991	7121	31
23	Deoria	728062	49247	52
24	Etah	448398	12938	21

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25	Etawah	400115	21220	48
26	Farrukhabad	489371	15376	27
27	Fatehpur	673062	23378	55
28	Firozabad	596573	22182	55
29	Gautam Buddha Nagar	203262	25193	79
30	Ghaziabad	589666	30562	103
31	Ghazipur	796733	32694	35
32	Gonda	785599	46432	92
33	Gorakhpur	1114802	110276	279
34	Hamirpur	356315	10385	37
35	Hapur	334155	17894	49
36	Hardoi	1111115	27350	62
37	Hathras	355649	18165	37
38	Jalaun	419643	28947	40
39	Jaunpur	1160119	41824	148
40	Jhansi	453877	22756	66
41	Kannauj	430421	17256	45
42	Kanpur Dehat	540905	27059	38
43	Kanpur Nagar	743317	41423	226
44	Kasganj	368577	15457	18
45	Kaushambi	450544	12055	34
46	Kheri	1036768	34221	82
47	Kushinagar	926269	46601	81
48	Lalitpur	285355	10661	23
49	Lucknow	841052	65671	322

50	Mahoba	252190	35900	49
51	Mahrajganj	771383	9565	24
52	Mainpuri	485964	18518	31
53	Mathura	549036	23715	88
54	Mau	641538	33752	53
55	Meerut	835890	50276	151
56	Mirzapur	701139	35900	78
57	Moradabad	1024711	93313	123
58	Muzaffarnagar	639857	42467	95
59	Pilibhit	775651	55608	49
60	Pratapgarh	948772	39122	87
61	Prayagraj	1053216	31645	186
62	Rae Bareli	893930	31719	87
63	Rampur	547193	38156	34
64	Saharanpur	1147499	89251	100
65	Sambhal	501703	21611	29
66	Sant Kabir Nagar	420678	33848	64
67	Shahjahanpur	801596	49305	65
68	Shamli	389712	42772	46
69	Shrawasti	318304	9940	23

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70	Siddharthnagar	520510	16635	26
71	Sitapur	1318879	51454	87
72	Sonbhadra	474136	17202	32
73	Sultanpur	715002	25203	90
74	Unnao	912113	37195	78
75	Varanasi	1176206	102981	224
Total		51408028	2819960	5845

Source: Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India

Over 34.04 crore Ayushman Cards have been created till now, out of which 15.50 crore cards have been made within 1 year. Hospitals lie at the cutting edge of services provided under the scheme. To ensure the effective participation of empanelled hospitals, growing and maintaining a wide network of hospitals actively participating in the scheme is imperative. In Uttar Pradesh, 51408028 Ayushman cards have been created, and 5845 hospital empanelments have been done till now

Conclusion

Uttar Pradesh has achieved substantial milestones under PMJAY, including issuing over 1.45 crore Ayushman Cards, allowing families access to cashless treatment worth up to ₹5 lakh annually. The state also leads with over 80 lakh OPD registrations under PMJAY-linked services, which include diagnostics, specialist consultations, and treatment for chronic conditions. By expanding the empanelment of private and public hospitals, the scheme has increased the availability of quality healthcare facilities across urban and rural areas. In Uttar Pradesh, PMJAY has emerged as a transformative initiative, significantly improving healthcare accessibility and financial protection for the underserved population. By empanelling a large network of public and private hospitals, the scheme has enabled low-income families to access quality secondary and tertiary care, which was previously unaffordable for many. The program has contributed to reducing catastrophic health expenditures, particularly for treatments like cancer, cardiac conditions, and maternity care. However, challenges such as limited awareness, disparities in rural and urban healthcare access, and gaps in primary healthcare infrastructure persist. To fully harness PMJAY's potential, Uttar Pradesh must focus on integrating the scheme with preventive and promotive healthcare services, strengthening primary care facilities, and addressing implementation bottlenecks. These efforts can ensure that PMJAY not only continues to alleviate immediate healthcare needs but also contributes to long-term health system resilience and equity in the state. PMJAY has made healthcare more inclusive and robust in Uttar Pradesh, addressing longstanding challenges such as financial barriers, inadequate infrastructure, and inequitable access to care.

Suggestions for the future Study To enhance the impact of PMJAY in Uttar Pradesh, several measures should be prioritized. First, targeted efforts are essential to address the healthcare needs of underserved and rural areas, including deploying mobile health units and increasing the empanelment of private hospitals in remote regions. Second, expanding awareness campaigns is critical to ensuring that all eligible families are informed about the benefits of the scheme and processes, particularly through community-based interventions like Ayushman Melas. Third, integrating robust data analytics and monitoring mechanisms can improve transparency, track outcomes, and optimize resource allocation. Lastly, incentivizing healthcare providers for preventive care services under PMJAY could shift the focus from curative to preventive measures, reducing the overall disease burden in the state

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